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35 INTRODUCTION

36

37 Madagascar's cities are the powerhouse of its economy, contributing three-quarters of the
38 national GDP, with the capital, Antananarivo, alone accounting for 44% [1]. Rapid urbanization in the
39 country, largely occurring without adequate planning and financing, has led to wide disadvantaged areas
40 with very poor infrastructures, acute service delivery challenges and high levels of informality in jobs
41 and housing. In such areas, highly degraded environmental conditions exacerbate inhabitants'
42 vulnerability to zoonotic infections and epidemics following limited access to education, health care as
43 well as everyday interactions with both domestic and wild animals [2,3]. In Madagascar, over 60% of
44 urban citizens live in such informal and unplanned settlements with a dearth of basic services, often
45 located in floodable, hazard-prone and high-risk areas [1]. These slum areas offer shelter and food to
46 small mammals (rodents, shrews) which are widespread and abundant [3–5], taking advantage of poor
47 trash collection, open sewers, very precarious and cluttered housing and omnipresence of standing water
48 [6,7]. In turn, rodents may greatly damage infrastructures, ravage or spoil foodstuffs, thus causing
49 potentially major economic losses for households [8–10]. Small mammals also contribute to infection
50 risk in both domestic animals and humans, as they may be source of numerous zoonotic pathogens,
51 sometimes with high epidemic potential [11]. In Madagascar, studies have demonstrated the carriage by
52 small mammals of a wide panel of zoonotic pathogens, including those responsible for various major
53 human diseases such as leptospirosis [12], plague [13,14], murine typhus [15] or Hantavirus disease
54 [16]. As such, the close promiscuity between humans and small mammals in precarious urban areas
55 constitute a major risk of zoonotic emergence that may lead to hardly controllable epidemics, especially
56 in case of possible shift from rodent-to-human to human-to-human transmission (e.g., plague) [3].

57 In such a context, it is crucial to document the ecology of these animals for the design of
58 appropriate control strategies. Among other knowledge, this requires to know about the order of
59 magnitude of their mobility for a reasonable spatial scaling of interventions, whatever they may be.
60 Unfortunately, small mammals, especially rodents' mobility within urban environments remains very
61 poorly documented. They are expected to exhibit different movement patterns between the habitats in
62 which they evolve, notably between urban, rural or natural areas [17]. However, previous studies have
63 mainly focused on non-urban environments [18,19], while surprisingly little information is available on
64 the mobility of small mammals in cities [20], as exemplified by the relatively little information available
65 in reviews on urban rat ecology [21,22]. To our knowledge, the mobility of urban small mammals has
66 been explored in only one single African urban settings, namely Morogoro, Tanzania [23].

67 In urban environments, rodents movements probably depend on the availability of food, water
68 and shelter, and they seem to cover relatively short distance [24,25]. The characteristics of the urban
69 environment may influence their mobility. For instance, with streets, large waterways, valleys identified
70 as important barriers to their displacements and gene flow between populations [17,26–28].

71 Several techniques have been used to track small mammals' movements in some urban areas
72 (reviewed in Byers et al., 2019), including direct measures like capture-mark-recapture (CMR) using
73 ear tags or PIT tags [29,30], which help monitor large numbers of rodents but are hindered by rodents'
74 neophobic nature [31]. Very High Frequency (VHF) telemetry and Global Positioning System (GPS)
75 tags are also used [32,33], though they face challenges in urban settings due to interference and high
76 costs [32,34]. In addition, both CMR and telemetry rely on the release of animals that may threaten
77 infrastructures, food security, animal and public health transmit pathogens, thus coming with obvious
78 ethical issues. Indirect methods, such as track marks and bait consumption, offer less labor-intensive
79 alternatives but come with trade-offs in power and accuracy [25]. Collective marking techniques, which
80 use persistent markers like fluorescein, xylenol orange, alizarin, or tetracycline, allow for rodent tracking
81 without the need for prior capture [35–38]. Rhodamine B, a non-toxic marker, efficiently colors
82 vibrissae and fur, and is metabolized in the liver [23,39,40]. It persists in vibrissae for up to 150 days,
83 making it suitable for short- and medium-term studies of rodent mobility [25,41].

84 Here, we propose the first survey of rodents' mobility in Antananarivo, the capital city of
85 Madagascar. Using Rhodamin-B-marked baits, we document distances that rats and mice may cover
86 within Antananarivo, and explore movement patterns within urban landscapes.

87

88 **MATERIALS AND METHODS**

89 **Ethical statements**

90 The present study was conducted as a part of the SCARIA project (coord. G. Dobigny, funded
91 by Belmont Forum) under the Research Permit number 182/22/MEDD/SG/DGGE/DAPRNE/SCBE.Re
92 delivered on the 28th June 2022 by the Malagasy Ministry of the Environment and Sustainable
93 Development. Ethical clearance for SCARIA was obtained on the 5th August 2021 from the National
94 Ethics Committee for Biomedical Research (number 097/MSANP/SG/AMM/CERBM). Field work
95 received agreement from the Director of Public Health for the Analamanga Region (visa of letter 03/24-
96 IPM/LaboPeste). The setting of traps in markets or households was conducted only after explicit oral
97 consent was obtained from local authorities (Fokontany heads and market presidents) as well as
98 inhabitants (households) and sellers (shops).

99 Small mammals were treated in accordance with the guidelines of the American Society of
100 mammalogists and were euthanized by cervical dislocation as recommended [42]. None of the four

101 species trapped during the present study (see below) is listed under a protected category by the IUCN
102 (red list category), and all are invasive species in Madagascar. Animal trapping and treatment procedures
103 used in this study received ethical clearance from the Committee for Animal Ethics of the Pasteur
104 Institute of Madagascar (001/2025/IPM/DS/CEA).

105

106 **Study area and periods**

107 Six areas with emblematic habitat characteristics were chosen (Fig 1). Ankasina (18.900S
108 47.505E) Andohatapenaka I (18.905S 47.502E) and II (18.892S 47.496E) lie in the western margin of
109 the city, on the fringe of the vast floodable rice-producing plain that runs north of Antananarivo. They
110 shelter very poor households that inhabit precarious habitats intermingled with rice fields. They are
111 characterized by the absence of roads, the absence of waste management and the omnipresence of
112 standing water. Situated in more central parts of the city, Isotry (19.907S 47.516E) and Andravoahangy
113 (18.896S 47.531E) markets are typical of Antananarivo markets: they are trade hotspots where lots of
114 goods (including food) are transported, stored and exchanged every day. They are very active and
115 frequented from dawn to dusk, but are almost empty during the night. They are surrounded by dense,
116 mostly hard-built, highly populated and rather poor districts. Finally, Ambodivona (18.892S 47.531E)
117 is also located within the poor, densely populated and mostly hard-built central zone of the city where
118 garbage dumpsters exist but often overflow. Each of these six sites were targeted to investigate rodents'
119 mobility in relation to slum environment (Ankasina and Andohatapenaka I and II), water drainage
120 channels (Ankasina), paved roads (Ambodivona and Andohatapenaka II), rice fields and built
121 environment interface (Ankasina and Andravoahangy), garbage dumping site (Ambodivona) and
122 markets (Isotry and Andravoahangy).

123

124 **Fig 1.** Location of the study sites within Antananarivo (GoogleEarth©)

125

126 Field work was conducted in all sites from May to July 2023 on the one hand, and further
127 completed in two sites (Ankasina and Isotry) in October 2023 on the other hand.

128 **Rhodamine B baiting**

129 Baits were made of a mixture of 750 g of peanut butter, 100 g of blended onion, two tablespoons
130 of peanut oil and 125 g of canned sardine. Rhodamine B (RB; Sigma-Aldrich©) was incorporated at a
131 dose of 0.5 g.kg⁻¹ of bait as previously described [19,40,41]. Although this concentration was already
132 demonstrated to be non-lethal and detectable for several days in rat whiskers, underfur and guard hairs
133 [40], including in Malagasy rodents [41], appetite, non-lethality and detectability of our RB-

134 containing baits (see below) were confirmed experimentally on wild *Rattus norvegicus* and *R. rattus* in
135 the IPM rodent-breeding house (data not shown).

136 In each studied urban site, a RB-containing bait area (hereafter designed as a “bait area”),
137 consisting of an area of <5 m², was selected according to the landscape elements to be investigated. As
138 such, in order to test whether water drain channels act as barrier to rodent mobility in Ankasina, RB-
139 containing pellets were deposited on one side of an open-sewer while traps were set on both sides. A
140 similar setup was used for testing the possible impact of paved roads in Ambodivona and
141 Andohatapenaka II. In Ankasina (sector III) and Andravoahangy, pellets were placed in rice fields to
142 evaluate rodent movement between rice fields and surrounding built environments. In order to assess
143 rodent mobility around markets, pellets were deposited in poorly maintained pipes around Isotry, or in
144 rice fields around Andravoahangy, where traps were set inside the markets. Lastly, pellets were placed
145 in garbage dumping sites, while traps were held in nearby households in Ambodivona. In each bait area,
146 5-10 pellets of 20 g of RB-containing baits were deposited out of sight and reach (e.g., ground cracks,
147 under-floors of houses, bush and holes along rice fields embankments) to minimize access by potential
148 non-target consumers (e.g., dogs, poultry) and to protect them from rain.

149 RB-containing baits were deposited the day before trapping, while pellets were checked,
150 weighted (when still partly, or completely present), removed and systematically renewed by fresh ones
151 every morning during the trapping campaigns (Fig 2).

152

153 **Fig 2.** Rhodamine B baiting and trapping protocol that was implemented in each site during five
154 (Ankasina) to six (other areas) successive days (i.e., three to four successive trapping nights,
155 respectively).

156

157 **Trapping protocol**

158 Trapping devices in Ankasina and Isotry were part of long-term rodent monitoring programs,
159 while in the other sites they have been specifically designed to place traps at increasing distances from
160 the marked bait and/or on either side of a targeted landscape feature. Locally made wire-mesh (WM)
161 and Sherman© traps (Sherman LFA, H.B. Sherman Traps Inc., Tallahassee, FL, USA) were
162 systematically used together since they were demonstrated to capture different species, thus allowing a
163 better sampling of small mammal diversity [43–45]. WM and Sherman traps were set in equal numbers
164 in rooms, farm animal enclosure, yards or market stalls at distances from RB-containing bait-areas
165 varying from a few to 400 meters. Traps were baited with a mixture of peanut butter, onion and canned
166 sardine and set for three (Ambodivona, Ankasina, Andohatapenaka and Andravoahangy) or four (Isotry)
167 successive nights. They were checked every morning: captured animals were collected and traps were

168 replaced, while empty traps were re-baited. Locations of each trap was recorded using a GPS (Garmin
169 eTrex 32x, Garmin Ltd., Olathe, KS, USA).

170 Captured rodents were processed immediately after traps' collect (i.e., within 2-5 hours). Since
171 small mammal biodiversity within Antananarivo is well documented and known to group only the black
172 rat *Rattus rattus*, the brown or Norway rat *R. norvegicus*, the house mouse *Mus musculus* and the Asian
173 shrew *Suncus murinus*, individuals were identified based on morphological characteristics only. Each
174 individual was euthanized by cervical dislocation, then weight and external characteristics (head and
175 body, tail, ear, hind-foot lengths) were measured. Sex was determined from external examination and
176 confirmed upon dissection. We chose to determine individual ages on the basis of reproductive organs
177 development rather than weight which may be misleading in some instances or seasons. As such, light
178 females (≤ 90 g) with closed vagina, undeveloped nipples together without embryo nor placental scars
179 on the one hand, and light males (≤ 90 g) with internal testicles and undeveloped seminal vesicles on
180 the other hand, were considered as juveniles. Individuals with fully developed reproductive organs,
181 embryos and/or placental scars were considered as adults.

182

183 **Rhodamine B detection in small mammals**

184 The presence of RB was investigated during dissection using a UV lamp pointed at the snout
185 and the abdominal cavity, essentially the digestive tract. In addition, at least six whiskers were sampled
186 from rats and stored at 4°C in the dark until they were observed under a fluorescent microscope
187 (Olympus©, Tokyo, Japan) with a 530–585 nm filter (WIY©) and an approximate magnification x10
188 for signs of RB fluorescence in the root and/or along the whisker shaft [34]. Only unambiguous signals
189 were considered positive (see examples on

190 Fig 3).

191

192 **Fig 3.** Examples of RB-positive individuals under UV light on the snout (A) and in the digestive tract
193 (B), as well as under fluorescence microscopy in the bulb (C) and in the stem (D) of the whisker.

194

195 **Data analysis**

196 Rodent relative abundance was estimated using trap success (i.e., the number of rats caught per
197 total number of trap-nights). Trapping efficiency by trap type and species was analyzed using the Chi-
198 squared (χ^2) test. Marking efficiency was evaluated by the number of marked rats out of the number of
199 captured rats. Individual rodent movement was measured under QGIS as the straight-line distance

200 between the GPS coordinates of the capture point and the nearest RB-baiting point. Mann-Whitney test
201 was applied to compare the distance travelled between species, as well as between sexes and age classes.

202

203 **RESULTS**

204

205 **Rodent trapping**

206 Overall, trapping campaigns were conducted over 46 days, yielding a total of 4,126 trap-nights
207 (2,063 of wire-meshed live traps and 2,063 of Sherman traps). These efforts resulted in a total of 595
208 captured small mammals, corresponding to an overall capture rate of 14.4%. Among the captured
209 animals, *Mus musculus* (251 individuals, 42.2% of all captures) and *Rattus norvegicus* (235 individuals,
210 39.5%) were the most represented species, followed by *Suncus murinus* (96 individuals, 16.1%) and *R.*
211 *rattus* (13 individuals, 2.2%). The Table 1 displays the number of captures per sites and per species.

212

213 **Rhodamine B marking**

214 Among all 595 captured small mammals, 116 (19.5%) showed unambiguous signs of RB
215 fluorescence (Table 1). Specifically, out of 235 *R. norvegicus* and 13 *R. rattus*, 109 (46.4%) and 5
216 (38.5%) were RB positive, respectively. Only two *M. musculus* out of 251 (0.8%) displayed RB signals,
217 while all 96 *S. murinus* were negative.

Table 1. Capture and RB marking results per species and trapping sites.

Site	<i>R. norvegicus</i>		<i>R. rattus</i>		<i>M. musculus</i>		<i>S. murinus</i>		Total
	N ^(a)	N Rhod. ^(b) (%)	N	N Rhod. (%)	N	N Rhod. (%)	N	N Rhod. (%)	
Ambodivona	8	7 (87.5%)	2	1 (50%)	6	-	7	-	8 (6.9%)
Andohatapenaka I	8	3 (37.5%)	-	-	7	-	1	-	3 (2.6%)
Andohatapenaka II	15	5 (33.3%)	-	-	30	-	1	-	5 (4.3%)
Andravoahangy	73	37 (50.7%)	-	-	1	-	11	-	37 (31.9%)
Ankasina	69	27 (39.1%)	11	4 (36.4%)	197	2 (1.02%)	24	-	33 (28.4%)
Isotry	62	30 (48.4%)	-	-	10	-	52	-	30 (25.9%)
Total	235	109 (46.4%)	13	5 (38.5%)	251	2 (0.8%)	96	-	116

219

^(a) **N:** Captured individuals

220

^(b) **N Rhod.:** RB-marked individuals

221

222 Out of the 116 RB-positive individuals, 61.2% showed fluorescence on the snout, 14.7% in
223 the digestive tract, 22.4% on the vibrissae, and 1.7% detected on rare parts such as eyes and embryos
224 (Table 2).

225

226 **Table 2.** Location of fluorescence detection in the different species. “Others” include RB signals that
227 were observed around the eyes as well as in embryos.

Species	Snout	Digestive tract	Whiskers	Others
<i>R. norvegicus</i>	68	13	26	2
<i>R. rattus</i>	3	2	-	-
<i>M. musculus</i>	-	2	-	-
Total	71	17	26	2

228

229 **Straight-line distances and urban landscape elements**

230 Over all RB-positive individuals, average traveled distances (i.e., straight-line distances
231 between the closest RB-containing bait areas and individual trapping points) were 88 m, ranging from
232 a minimum of 1 m to a maximum of 265.8 m. When considering species-specific data, average and
233 maximum distances were 86.7 m and 265.8 m in *R. norvegicus*, and 152.4 m and 250.7 m in *R. rattus*,
234 respectively; no significant difference in average distances were observed between the two rat species
235 ($p = 0.078$) (Fig 4). Importantly, we can confidently state that the longest straight-line distance recorded
236 for *R. norvegicus* was travelled by an animal captured during the first trapping night (Fig 4), meaning
237 this distance was travelled within one single day. The two RB-positive mice were males that were caught
238 at 1 m and at 53.3 m meters away from the baiting areas (Fig 4). Only *R. norvegicus* sample size allowed
239 us to investigate distances according to sex and age: no significant difference was found between males
240 and females ($p = 0.203$), but traveled distances were significantly higher in juveniles (118.7 meters in
241 average) than in adults (80.7 meters) ($p = 0.03$).

242

243 **Fig 4.** Straight-line distances traveled by rodents according to their species, age, sex and night of
244 capture

245

246 Trapping and fluorescent results unambiguously show that four RB positive brown rats have
247 crossed the Ankasina drainage channel (Fig 5A), while another positive one has moved through a
248 cobblestone road in Andohatapenaka II (Fig 5B). Many positive RB-positive *R. norvegicus* were caught
249 inside both Isotry and Andravoahangy markets even though the marked baits were placed outside the

250 market, i.e., within adjacent rice fields in Andravoahangy, and in neighboring streets (> 50 meters) in
251 Isotry. Maximal straight-line distances between outside market baiting areas to inside markets capture
252 points in these two settings reached 217 m in Andravoahangy and 101.3 m in Isotry (Fig 5D and Fig
253 5E). Our results also show several instances of rats' displacement between rice fields and nearby houses
254 (Ankasina III; Fig 5C) as well as from rice fields and adjacent market (Andravoahangy, Fig 5D). These
255 movements corresponded to straight-line distances up to 265.8 m and 217 m for *R. norvegicus* in
256 Ankasina III (Fig 5C) and Andravoahangy (Fig 5E), respectively, and 250.7 m for *R. rattus* in Ankasina
257 III (Fig 5C). Likewise, rodents' mobility between dumping sites and surrounding houses were
258 demonstrated to reach at least 105 m and 35 m at Ambodivona (Fig 5F) and Andohatapenaka I (Fig 5G),
259 respectively.

260

261 **Fig 5.** Experimental design and trapping results showing RB-positive and RB-negative captures of
262 *Rattus norvegicus* and *R. rattus* in (A) Ankasina, sector II, (B) Andohatapenaka II, (C) Ankasina, sector
263 III, (D) Andravoahangy market, (E) Isotry market, (F) Ambodivona and (G) Andohatapenaka I.

264

265 **DISCUSSION**

266

267 The trapping success observed in our study (14.4%) is quite high and confirmed that small
268 mammals are abundant within Antananarivo, as already observed in previous murine surveillance
269 campaigns carried out in several urban districts of the Malagasy capital from 1998 to 2001 [12,14,46,47].
270 Our survey includes the systematic use of both wire-mesh and Sherman© traps, thus allowing us to
271 provide a more accurate view of the small mammal diversity within the city. Indeed, while previous
272 studies relied only on wire-mesh traps, thus essentially capturing rats, Sherman© traps were very useful
273 here in showing the relative abundance of house mice and shrews within the city which, together, make
274 up to more than half of all captures. This echoes previous recommendations about the importance of the
275 concomitant use of several types of traps to assess small mammal diversity in other African settings
276 [43–45,48].

277 Investigations of small mammals' mobility and space use usually rely on capture-mark-
278 recapture (CMR) procedures. However, such approaches appear unsuitable for the study of pest species
279 that thrive in highly anthropized socio-ecosystems since the release of unwanted and/or noxious animals
280 is ethically unacceptable. The use of fluorochrome like Rhodamine B provides imperfect pieces of
281 information since it allows one to access only minimal (i.e., straight-line) distances that positive animals
282 have travelled. With the potential exception of exceptionally linear habitats like sewers or shores, such
283 results should probably not be used to infer true individual distances that animals indeed walked through
284 the urban landscape – thus also greatly limiting the value of statistic-based comparisons. However, these

285 methods appear as a suitable alternative to depict general trends of movement in urban settings due to
286 easy implementation, low cost, unambiguous results and ethical acceptability. In particular, they provide
287 valuable knowledge to define “areas” hence scales at which management strategies should be designed.

288 In Antananarivo, when all species are combined, 19.5% of trapped individuals were RB-
289 positive. However, no shrew and only two house mice were positive, while all other positive RB-marked
290 animals belong to *R. norvegicus* and *R. rattus*. This makes species-specific ratios of RB-positive animals
291 much higher, reaching 46.4% in brown rats and 38.5% in black rats. These values are comparable or
292 higher than those observed for rats in other urban settings (e.g., 27.9% of *R. norvegicus* in Salvador,
293 Brazil [25]; 12.2% of *R. norvegicus* and *R. rattus* in Morogoro, Tanzania [23]) or in other rural Malagasy
294 areas (e.g., 2.5% to 59.3% of *R. rattus* depending on the habitat and the season [19]). As such, our study
295 confirms the value of Rhodamine B as a good biological marker for investigating the mobility of rats
296 within urban socio-ecosystems.

297

298 Studies of rats’ mobility in cities are relatively scarce: a recent review recorded 39 studies, of
299 which only 28 relied on direct observations (i.e., excluding genetics-based inferences) such as bait
300 uptake, telemetry of CMR (see Supplemental Material in Byers et al., 2019). With the exception of
301 average daily distance of 200 meters observed in Copenhagen sewers, Denmark, this review suggests
302 that maximum distances never exceed 165 meters (see Supplementary Material in Byers et al., 2019),
303 with the exception of the only study mentioned from Africa, namely El Motia, Egypt, where authors
304 observed distances for *R. rattus* up to 250 meters [49]. In Morogoro, Tanzania, Mohr and colleagues
305 (2007; not included in Byers et al.’s review) used RB-containing baits along linear trapping devices,
306 starting from the baiting area (i.e., 0 meter) to 20, 50, 100 then 200 meters distant trapping points. Most
307 positive black rats were captured at 0 (N=2 positive animals out of 20 captures), 20 (1/2) or 50 (2/14)
308 meters while none of the 10 individuals trapped at 100 or 200 meters displayed RB signals. Only three
309 *R. norvegicus* were captured: one out of two at 0 meter was positive; the third individual was found 200
310 meters away and was RB negative (see their Table 1). In Salvador, Brazil, Awoniyi et al. (2021)
311 implemented RB-based linear trapping device, too, with trapping points located at 15, 30 and 60 meters
312 away along three lines, and 15, 30, 60 and 90 meters away along a fourth line (see their Fig 1). They
313 focused on the most abundant species, *R. norvegicus*, and found RB-positive individuals at 15 (N=3
314 positive animals out of 9 captures), 30 (2/9), 60 (4/17) and 90 (3/8) meters (see their Table 1). The latter
315 study suggests that Norway rats rather frequently travel at least 90 meters (straight-line distances)
316 throughout the urban landscape; unfortunately, their experimental device cannot provide insights into
317 potentially longer distances.

318 In Antananarivo, we found that rats covered an average distance of 90 meters, with several
319 records over 150 meters (N=40) and up to 265 meters observed by an adult male *R. norvegicus* that

320 walked this distance within one single day. One should keep in mind that these values are straight-line
321 distances, thus representing probably strongly under-estimated truly travelled distances. Overall, our
322 results indicate that, in Antananarivo, both Norway and black rats walk much longer distances than
323 described to date in the literature by direct methods. Accordingly, indirect approaches, namely
324 population genetics analyses and likelihood computation of first generation migrants analysis, have
325 suggested that most urban *R. norvegicus* showed strong site-fidelity (62 meters) while a few individuals
326 may travel much longer theoretical distances (i.e., 2-11.5 kilometers) within Baltimore city, USA [50].

327 *R. norvegicus* is usually perceived as a poorly mobile species in cities, with food resources
328 driving its displacements while urban features limit its movements [17]. However, most data available
329 to date are based on studies conducted in well-developed and often “Western world” cities. Accordingly,
330 many experimental designs as well as results’ interpretation are viewed from the “city blocks”
331 perspective (Byers et al., 2019, and the included Supplementary Material). In addition, long distances
332 movements of Norway rats were interpreted as resulting from urban landscape disturbance (e.g, building
333 demolition) or rodent management programs that trigger migration [17]. Yet, the only two studies
334 focusing on poor urban areas and slums in the Global South that we are aware of (namely, Salvador,
335 Brazil: Awoniyi et al., 2021; Ankasina and Andohatapenaka, Antananarivo, Madagascar: this study)
336 tend to show that *R. norvegicus* walk straight-line distances of 90 meters and more on a very regular
337 basis. Yet, no major urban landscape modification or rodent control was noted before or during these
338 experiments. In addition, slums largely consist in houses made of highly precarious and rat-permeable
339 materials. Moreover, they are characterized by agricultural food stocks within households, widespread
340 breeding activities (e.g., cattle and poultry) as well as very poor to absence of waste management which
341 are expected to provide abundant and widespread resources for rodents [3]. From there, we speculate
342 that poor urban environments are more permeable to rodents which may travel longer distances than
343 usually observed in more formal hard-built urban settings.

344 We also found that juvenile *R. norvegicus* individuals travelled significantly greater straight-
345 line distances compared to adults. Although strait-line distances do not necessarily reflect distances truly
346 walked by rats, meaning that they should be handled with great care, such a difference is not unexpected.
347 Indeed, Norway rats are social animals and they are organized in often large colonies with dominance-
348 based hierarchy [22]. In particular, dominating adults may remain inside their own territory where they
349 defend access to resources and chase newcomers; in the contrary, young subordinate individuals may
350 have to explore larger areas to find food and/or sexual partners within, or even beyond the colony’s
351 territory.

352 Gene flow between spatially distinct populations does not directly measure movements between
353 their respective areas since individuals may move close to, but no reproduce with allopatric congeners.
354 However, the coincidence of low gene flow between two pools of individuals on the one hand, and the

355 existence of a putative ecological or physical barrier between them may sign barriers to gene flow which,
356 in turn, may be interpreted as true barriers to mobility. Previous genetic studies conducted in urban rats'
357 populations from American (New York and New Orleans) [26], Canadian (Vancouver) [26], Brazilian
358 (Salvador) [26,51] and Beninese (Cotonou) [52] cities have identified such genetic discontinuities that
359 were associated with potential physical barriers that may indeed limit animals' mobility. Among them
360 were valleys, less human-populated areas, highways and great rivers. Highways were also identified as
361 significant barriers to rat mobility by CMR and bait uptake-based investigations (reviewed in Byers et
362 al., 2019). Conversely, some ecological studies and rodent management analyses suggested that some
363 urban features facilitate rats' movements (e.g., urban parks, sewers; reviewed in Byers et al., 2019).
364 However, once again, most studies addressing rats' displacements across urban landscapes were
365 conducted in Western, mostly American cities. As far as we know, data from socio-environmentally
366 degraded urban areas, especially slums, are inexistent.

367 In Antananarivo, we found that a minor paved road (Andohatapenaka II and Ambodivona) as
368 well as a water drainage channels (Ankasina II) had been crossed by rats in several instances. This was
369 rather expected since most roads in Antananarivo are narrow (rarely more than 6-8 meters) and traffic
370 is almost null at night. In addition, several cement- or wood-made bridges step over most drainage
371 channels, at least in Ankasina II where we made our own observations.

372 We also unambiguously demonstrated that Norway rats were very regularly moving between
373 markets and their surroundings, whatever they may be (e.g., rice fields in Andravoahangy; hard-built
374 city in Isotry). We cannot assure that the rats come from outside to feed inside the markets, or vice-
375 versa. However, lots of food items (rice and other grains, beans, fruits, vegetables, meat, fish, living and
376 dead poultry, etc) are sold in most Antananarivo markets, and many stocks, remains and wastes lie on
377 the floor. As such, they are expected to be very attractive resource hotspots for rats. Our results also
378 show that, once inside, rodents may circulate widely throughout the market. This was particularly
379 notable in Andravoahangy market where a high number of RB-positive *R. norvegicus* were trapped
380 around poultry shops that were yet more than 150 meters away from RB bait area (see Fig 5D). This
381 supports some particular food resources hotspot as being particularly attractive for rats, even from long
382 distances. Our findings in the Malagasy capital city are consistent with those found in Morogoro,
383 Tanzania, where rodents roam up 100 meters towards market, butcheries and grain store [23].

384 In Isotry, a network of subterranean but poorly managed pipes converge to the market. Our
385 observations in the field suggest that this network may facilitate rats' mobility towards as well as
386 throughout (i.e., under) the market. Infrastructures such as buried or semi-buried pipes were already
387 shown to facilitate rodents' movements within urban landscapes (e.g., sewers in Copenhagen, Denmark;
388 [53]).

389 Similar pattern may exist for garbage dumpster as observed in Ambodivona where rats were
390 trapped at 8, 18, 25, 30 and 105 meters away from the dump after a contact with RB-containing baits.
391 However, our experimental device does not allow us to investigate how far rats may travel to forage at
392 garbage dumpsters.

393 Finally, we found that rat exchanges were rather frequent between rice fields and households,
394 sometimes implying long distances, namely >50 meters for *R. norvegicus* and up to 250 meters for *R.*
395 *rattus* (Fig. 5C). In this particular case, it is difficult to argue about the reason for rats' mobility between
396 the two habitats. Our experiment took place in Ankasina in June 2023 when it is characterized by mild
397 temperatures and a dry climate, coinciding with the rice harvest season. Two RB-positive *R. rattus* were
398 caught approximately 200 meters away from the RB-baiting point. In rural areas of Madagascar, this
399 species represents the majority of captured rodents in rice fields and sisal hedges surrounding farms
400 [19,41]. In such habitats, black rats can travel up to 350 meters and could potentially move between
401 neighborhoods in search of food resources or suitable habitat [19].

402 The sometimes-long-distance movements that we have documented in Antananarivo may have
403 important consequences in terms of urban rodent management. First, they imply that zoonotic pathogens
404 may circulate widely across the city over very short periods (i.e., one to a few days). For instance,
405 Madagascar is a plague-endemic country, accounting for approximately 80% of human cases reported
406 worldwide [54]. Though usually perceived as a rural disease, urban bubonic plague cases (i.e., rat-to-
407 human) are regularly recorded in cities, including Mahajanga [55,56] and, more recently, Toamasina
408 and Antananarivo regions during the 2017 large epidemic [57]. In Madagascar, the control is based on
409 rodent and flea control in and around plague-positive homes (within a radius of 200 meters for fleas, but
410 no spatial recommendation for rodents) [58,59]. Yet, our study shows that rats (which are among the
411 most likely mammal reservoirs of the plague bacillus, *Y. pestis*) can travel around distances up to 250
412 meters throughout the urban landscape. This suggests that intervention areas should be significantly
413 widen during riposte to bubonic plague cases in Malagasy cities.

414 In addition, markets are often quoted as important targets for rodent control, including in the
415 framework of riposte to plague [60]. Considering markets attractiveness for urban rats, our results
416 suggest that this may indeed have effects on rat populations at least several dozens of meters around,
417 but that implementation procedures (e.g., quantity and distribution of baiting areas, traps, etc.) must take
418 such a scale into consideration.

419 Finally, we showed that rats move frequently (sometimes over quite long distances) between
420 urban rice fields and the surrounding urban hard-built landscape (here, households and markets). This
421 result has significant consequences in terms of rodent management in Antananarivo where rice fields
422 inside the urban tissue *per se* are numerous and crucial from both food production and socio-cultural
423 perspectives [61], but also in other African cities where urban market gardening has been shown to

424 produce potential rodent-associated hazards for human health (e.g., [62]). Indeed, actions against pest
425 rodents in agricultural vs. built environments usually rely on different approaches, and they may be
426 implemented by different sectorial services. For instance, in Madagascar, the agriculture sector is in
427 charge of rodent management in case of damages to crops, while rodent control within houses is usually
428 driven by health authorities as a reactive process to plague outbreaks [63]. While targeting only field (or
429 house) rats may marginally and provisionally impact house (or field) infestations, there is little doubt
430 that permeability between the two habitats will make control inefficient, especially on the long term. As
431 such, in Global South cities, tight promiscuity between fields and households on the one hand, and
432 rodent exchanges between the two habitats on the other hand, imposes to consider such areas as a unique
433 management spatial unit, hence to coordinate operational efforts between sectors.

434

435

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